

ECONOMIC SECURITY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES: EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INSTRUMENTS

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Abstract. The article examines the role of Artificial intelligence (AI) as an increasingly important tool for ensuring the economic security of industrial enterprises. Analyzed the level of development of AI in Uzbekistan, highlighted governmental strategy and support in this area. Furthermore, experience of foreign developed countries in using AI instruments in ensuring economic security of industrial enterprises, such as USA, China and Japan were analyzed.

Keywords Artificial Intelligence (AI), instrument, economic security, industrial enterprise, foreign, experience, risk, analysis, cybersecurity

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming an increasingly important tool for ensuring the economic security of industrial enterprises. Its use can significantly reduce risks, increase the efficiency and competitiveness of enterprises.

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) in Uzbekistan has become a priority for the state, especially in recent years. The country seeks to introduce advanced technologies in various sectors of the economy and management. In 2021, a strategy for the development of AI for 2021-2022 was developed and adopted, which identified key areas for the implementation of AI in the economy, education, healthcare and public administration [1]. As part of this strategy, specialized centers and institutes, such as the Innovation Center for the Development of Artificial Intelligence, were created to support the development and implementation of AI.

The state actively supports the creation of technology parks and business incubators, where startups and small businesses can develop and implement AI technologies. At the same time, the Government of Uzbekistan provides grants and subsidies to support AI projects, which stimulates scientific research and the development of innovative solutions. Despite this, in some areas of AI development, the country still lags comparing to the world's developed countries, where AI is successfully implemented in various spheres, such as in the process of ensuring economic security of industrial enterprises.

II. METHODS

To investigate the intersection of economic security and AI development, a comprehensive review of relevant literature and case studies was conducted. Academic journals, industry reports, and reputable sources were consulted to gather insights on experience of foreign developed countries in using AI instruments in ensuring economic security of industrial enterprises.

III. RESULTS

The Global Centre for Governance of AI's Global Index for Responsible AI (GIRAI) has ranked Uzbekistan as the leading country in Central Asia in responsible artificial intelligence [2]. With a score of 11.27, Uzbekistan ranks 70th globally out of 138 countries assessed in the study. The country's success has been bolstered by three presidential decrees aimed at advancing AI. These decrees cover key areas including cultural and linguistic diversity, international cooperation, public sector skills development, antitrust enforcement, and transparency.

GIRAI assesses responsible AI across 19 thematic areas, divided into three main dimensions: human rights and AI, responsible AI governance, and responsible AI capabilities. The study, which involved 16 regional centres, including the Institute for the Development of Freedom of Information (IDFI) for Eastern Europe and Central Asia, assesses each country based on government structures, actions, and initiatives of non-state actors (fig.).

Fig. Dimensions of the responsible AI index.

Kazakhstan follows with a result that places it 74th in the world. The country leads in government initiatives related to AI, including a notable project on social protection for gig economy workers, launched in July 2022.

Kyrgyzstan ranks third in the region with a score of 7.4, demonstrating notable non-governmental sector engagement in responsible AI. However, the lack of comprehensive government structures weighs on its overall score.

Tajikistan is the only country in Central Asia with a national AI strategy aimed at development through 2040. Despite its strong performance in responsible AI governance, its non-governmental sector is limited.

Turkmenistan, with the lowest regional score of 1.98, ranks 111th globally. The country lacks significant government structures for responsible AI and has minimal non-governmental sector involvement, resulting in a score of zero for responsible AI capabilities.

Although in some areas of AI development, the country still lags behind developed countries, where AI is successfully implemented in various areas, including in the process of ensuring the economic security of industrial enterprises.

Artificial intelligence (AI) plays a significant role in ensuring the economic security of enterprises in developed countries [3]. Here are the main ways in which AI helps in this area:

1. Data analysis and risk forecasting: AI can process large amounts of data, identify trends and anomalies, which allows you to predict financial risks and identify potential threats to the business. This helps companies take measures in advance to prevent losses.

2. Cybersecurity: AI is actively used to protect enterprises from cyberattacks. It

can detect suspicious activity, analyze user and system behavior, and automatically respond to threats. This is especially important for protecting financial and commercial data.

3. Optimization of financial operations: AI helps automate and optimize financial processes such as cost management, tax planning, and investment strategies. This reduces the likelihood of errors and improves the efficiency of financial resource management.

4. Fraud Detection: AI can analyze transactions and other financial operations in real time, identifying suspicious behavior and preventing fraud. This is especially relevant for the banking and e-commerce sectors.

5. Supply Chain Management: AI helps predict market changes, optimize inventory and logistics, which reduces the risks associated with supply chain disruptions. This ensures business stability and resilience.

6. Monitoring Regulatory Changes: AI can track changes in laws and regulations, analyze their impact on business, and suggest appropriate corrective measures. This helps businesses stay compliant and avoid fines.

7. Planning and Scenario Modeling: AI allows us to model various economic scenarios and their impact on business, which helps companies better prepare for possible crises or market changes.

IV. DISCUSSION

In developed countries, AI is actively integrated into business processes to ensure the resilience and security of companies, helping them cope with modern challenges more effectively. It is important to consider the experience of foreign countries in ensuring the economic security of enterprises. In particular, the experience of USA, China and Japan.

In the United States, there is a wide range of artificial intelligence (AI) tools that businesses use to ensure economic security. These tools include solutions for data analytics, predictive analytics, process automation, risk management, cybersecurity, and other key aspects. Here are some of the most significant AI tools used for these purposes [4]:

Data Analytics and Predictive Analytics Platforms

- SAS: SAS offers powerful analytics tools that help businesses analyze large volumes of data, identify trends, and predict risks. This is especially useful for managing financial and operational risks.

- IBM Watson: Watson provides a set of tools for data analytics, predictive analytics, and business process automation. Watson is also used to analyze text data such as documents and reports, which helps in risk assessment and decision making.

- Palantir: This platform helps companies integrate and analyze large volumes of

heterogeneous data, which helps improve risk management, including financial and operational risks.

Cybersecurity

- Darktrace: Using AI to create a company's "immune system," Darktrace monitors network activity and detects anomalies that may indicate cyberattacks. This system helps protect sensitive data and prevent security breaches.
- CrowdStrike Falcon: This solution uses AI to monitor and protect workstations and servers from cyberthreats. It provides real-time detection, investigation, and response to cyberattacks.
- FireEye Helix: FireEye offers an AI-powered platform for incident management and cyberattack investigation. The tool allows you to integrate security data from various sources and automate incident response.

Financial Risk Management Instruments

- Kensho: Developed by S&P Global, the platform uses AI to analyze financial data and predict economic events. Kensho helps investors and financial institutions predict the impact of various factors on markets and minimize financial risks.
- Zest AI: This platform uses AI to assess creditworthiness and manage risk in lending. It enables financial institutions to make more informed decisions and reduce loan default risks.
- Ayasdi: Ayasdi uses AI to analyze complex data and identify hidden patterns that can help manage financial risks and make strategic decisions.

Business Process Automation and Optimization Instruments

- UiPath: UiPath offers robotic process automation (RPA) solutions that automate routine tasks such as transaction processing, document management, and data management. This reduces the risk of errors and improves operational efficiency.
- Automation Anywhere: This platform also provides RPA solutions and uses AI to optimize business processes, improving cost management and increasing task accuracy.
- Blue Prism: Blue Prism offers tools to create a digital workforce that can perform tasks ranging from data processing to customer interactions, helping to reduce operational risks.

Supply Chain Management Instruments

- ClearMetal: This platform uses AI to analyze and optimize supply chains. ClearMetal enables demand forecasting, inventory management, and mitigation of supply chain risks.
- Llamasoft: Llamasoft provides supply chain modeling and optimization tools that enable businesses to improve inventory management, demand forecasting, and mitigation of logistics risks.
- Resilinc: Resilinc uses AI to monitor supply chain risks and offer mitigation solutions, helping businesses build resilience in the face of global crises: Compliance

Management Tools

- Thomson Reuters CLEAR: This solution uses AI to automate compliance processes, including KYC (Know Your Customer) and AML (Anti-Money Laundering). CLEAR helps businesses reduce the risks associated with non-compliance.

- NAVEX Global: NAVEX provides enterprise compliance management tools, including incident management, employee training, and monitoring of regulatory changes. AI is used to analyze data and automate compliance processes.

- LogicGate: LogicGate offers a risk and compliance management platform that uses AI to automate risk management, threat assessment, and compliance processes.

Green Safety Tools

- Ecova: Ecova uses AI to monitor and analyze energy consumption, emissions, and other environmental metrics. This helps businesses reduce their environmental footprint and meet environmental standards.

- Enablon: This platform offers tools to manage health, safety, and environmental compliance. AI helps automate performance monitoring and risk assessment.

- SP Global Environmental Solutions: SP Global's solutions use AI to analyze environmental and sustainability data to help companies make decisions that reduce their environmental impact.

These tools enable U.S. businesses to not only ensure economic security, but also improve efficiency, resilience, and competitiveness in a rapidly changing global economy.

Along with the United States, China is also at the forefront of developing and applying AI in many areas of life. The country has many artificial intelligence (AI) tools that are actively used to ensure the economic security of enterprises [5]. As one of the world leaders in the development and implementation of AI, China offers a wide range of solutions aimed at data analysis, cybersecurity, risk management, and business process optimization. Here are some of the main AI tools used to ensure the economic security of enterprises in China:

Data Analysis and Predictive Analytics

- Alibaba Cloud AI: Alibaba provides AI-powered solutions for big data analytics, which helps enterprises manage risks and optimize operations. Alibaba Cloud AI offers tools for predictive analytics, market analysis, and supply chain management.

- Baidu AI Cloud: Baidu offers a platform that uses AI to analyze data and predict risks. These tools allow enterprises to improve decision-making processes and ensure resilience in the face of uncertainty.

- Tencent Cloud AI: Tencent provides tools for data analysis and risk management using AI. The platform helps enterprises analyze market trends, manage operational risks, and forecast financial performance.

Cybersecurity

- Qihoo 360: Qihoo 360 is one of the largest cybersecurity companies in China, offering AI-powered solutions to protect enterprise data and systems from cyber threats. Their platforms use AI to analyze network traffic, detect threats, and prevent cyber attacks.

- Ant Financial AI Security: Alibaba subsidiary Ant Financial has developed AI security tools for the financial sector, including fraud prevention, data protection, and cybersecurity. These solutions are widely used in banks and other financial institutions.

- Tencent Security: Tencent provides cybersecurity solutions that use AI to detect and prevent threats. Their tools help enterprises protect their networks, data, and applications from cyber attacks.

Financial Risk Management Instruments

- Ping An Technology: Ping An, one of the largest insurance companies in China, has developed many AI-powered solutions for financial risk management. Their tools help assess creditworthiness, manage investment portfolios, and predict economic trends.

- JD Digits (JD Finance): JD Digits uses AI to analyze financial data, predict risks, and manage assets. The platform helps companies optimize investment strategies and reduce financial risks.

- SenseTime: SenseTime, a leader in computer vision, provides financial risk management solutions using AI to analyze and process big data. Their technology is used in banks and financial institutions to assess credit risks and prevent fraud.

- iFlytek: iFlytek is one of the leaders in natural language processing and speech recognition in China. Their solutions are used to automate business processes, including document processing, voice interfaces, and automated communication with customers.

- Yitu Technology: Yitu develops AI solutions for business process optimization, such as intelligent video surveillance systems and data analytics, which can be used to manage operational risks and improve security.

- Megvii (Face++): Known for its computer vision and facial recognition solutions, Megvii also offers tools for business process automation, access management, and security.

Another country that has successfully implemented AI tools in the field of economic security of enterprises is Japan. Today, in the land of the rising sun, there are many tools based on artificial intelligence (AI) that are used to ensure the economic security of enterprises. Here are some of them [6]:

AI-based Cybersecurity Solutions

- NTT Security: A division of NTT Group, offers AI-based solutions to protect companies from cyberattacks. Their systems use machine learning to analyze traffic, identify threats, and prevent attacks in real time.

- Trend Micro: A Japanese company that develops information security software uses AI to analyze malware and threats. The company's solutions automatically block

suspicious activity and improve the protection of corporate networks.

AI-driven Risk Management Platforms

- Fujitsu Risk Intelligence: A platform that uses AI to assess risks in supply chains. It helps predict possible disruptions, analyze supplier data, and identify weaknesses in logistics, thereby reducing economic risks.

- Hitachi AI-driven Risk Assessment: Hitachi has developed a platform that uses AI to analyze financial risks and make decisions. It helps companies assess credit risks and optimize financial strategies.

Predictive Analytics Instruments

- SoftBank AI Predictive Analytics: SoftBank offers AI-powered analytics tools that help companies anticipate market changes and assess economic risks. These solutions analyze sales, demand, and trend data to help businesses adapt to changes.

- NEC AI Predictive System: NEC develops predictive analytics systems that help companies anticipate economic threats, such as market changes or competitors' behavior, and take preventive measures. AI in Supply Chain Management

- Mitsubishi Electric AI-driven Supply Chain Management: Mitsubishi Electric uses AI to optimize supply chains. Their systems help companies analyze logistics and supply chain data, anticipate potential disruptions, and reduce costs.

- Kawasaki Heavy Industries AI-based Supply Chain Monitoring: Kawasaki incorporates AI into supply chain monitoring systems to predict supply chain risks and respond quickly to changes.

AI-powered Financial Security Instruments

- Nomura Research Institute (NRI) AI Fraud Detection: NRI has developed AI-powered instruments to detect financial fraud and transaction anomalies. These solutions help companies detect suspicious activity and protect their assets.

- MUFG AI Financial Analysis: Mitsubishi UFJ Financial Group uses AI to analyze financial data and predict economic threats such as defaults or currency fluctuations.

AI-driven HR and Workforce Management

- Recruit Holdings AI HR Solutions: Recruit Holdings develops AI-powered solutions for HR management, including recruitment, training, and assessment of employees. These tools help optimize HR processes and minimize risks associated with the human factor.

- Workday AI-driven HR Analytics: Workday provides AI-powered analytics solutions that help companies manage their workforce and anticipate changes in the labor market.

Automated Business Process Management

- RPA (Robotic Process Automation) by UiPath Japan: UiPath offers AI-powered business process automation solutions. This helps companies reduce their reliance on

human factors, reduce costs, and improve management efficiency.

- Blue Prism Japan AI-driven Automation: Blue Prism incorporates AI into business process automation, enabling businesses to efficiently manage operations and minimize risks associated with errors and delays.

These instruments and solutions help Japanese companies stay competitive and secure in the global economy by using AI to manage risks and ensure business security.

V. CONCLUSION

For Uzbekistan, as a developing country with a growing economy, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into ensuring the economic security of enterprises can become an important factor in sustainable growth and competitiveness. Here are some recommendations in this regard:

1. Developing a National Strategy on AI

- Objective: Creating a national strategy covering all aspects of the use of AI, including the economic security of enterprises.

- What to include: Supporting research and development, training specialists, forming a regulatory framework and stimulating investment in AI.

2. Investing in data infrastructure

- Objective: Creating a reliable and scalable data infrastructure for analyzing and processing large volumes of information.

- What to include: Providing access to high-quality data, developing data centers and cloud technologies.

3. Training and professional development

- Objective: Training specialists capable of implementing and maintaining AI systems at enterprises.

- What to include: Introducing specialized training programs at universities, creating advanced training courses, stimulating the exchange of experience with international experts.

4. Startup and Small Business Support

- Objective: Promoting AI innovation among small and medium-sized enterprises.

- What to include: Creating incubators and accelerators, providing grants and tax incentives, developing a venture capital network.

5. AI Regulation and Standardization

- Objective: Providing a legal and ethical framework for the use of AI.

- What to include: Developing quality and security standards for AI systems, regulating access to data, protecting privacy and complying with ethical standards.

6. Integrating AI into Public Administration

- Objective: Using AI to improve the efficiency and transparency of public administration.

- What to include: Implementing AI in systems for monitoring and forecasting

economic risks, automating decision-making and data analysis.

7. Creating platforms for sharing experience

- Objective: Developing cooperation between enterprises, the government and scientific institutions.

- What to include: Organizing forums, conferences and working groups on AI issues, creating online platforms for sharing experience and best practices.

8. Implementation of AI in risk management

- Objective: Use of AI to identify and prevent threats to economic security.

- What to include: Development of financial risk forecasting systems, market monitoring and analysis of competitors' behavior.

9. Support for international cooperation

- Objective: Involvement of Uzbekistan in international projects and programs on AI.

- What to include: Participation in international initiatives, exchange of technologies and experience with other countries, attraction of foreign investment in the development of AI.

10. Creation of a favorable business environment

- Objective: Simplification of procedures and creation of conditions for the implementation of AI in enterprises.

- What to include: Facilitation of access to AI technologies, reduction of bureaucratic barriers, and stimulation of entrepreneurial activity.

These recommendations can help strengthen the economic security of enterprises in Uzbekistan, as well as increase the country's competitiveness in the international arena.

To conclude, artificial intelligence is a powerful tool that can significantly improve the economic security of industrial enterprises, improving their ability to predict and manage risks, optimize production processes and protect against cyber threats. The introduction of AI in industry contributes not only to increased efficiency, but also to the long-term sustainability of business in the face of uncertainty and competition. In developed foreign countries, AI is actively integrated into business processes to ensure the sustainability and security of companies, helping them to cope more effectively with modern challenges.

References

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of February 17, 2021 No. PP-4996
"About measures for creation of conditions for the accelerated implementation of technologies of artificial intelligence".
2. Results of Global Index on Responsible AI in Eastern Europe and Central Asia. https://idfi.ge/en/girai_ee_and_ca
3. R Kholikova. Issues of ensuring economic security in industrial enterprises of the republic of Uzbekistan. Journal Science and innovation, 2024. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/issues-of-ensuring-economic-security-in-industrial-enterprises-of-the-republic-of-uzbekistan>
4. Kasimov, S, Kholikova R. (2020). Classification of enterprise goals in strategic management at cotton processing complex. Journal of Critical Reviews, 7(6), pp. 625–630.
5. R Kholikova. Experience of Foreign Countries in Application of Ai Instruments to Ensure the Economic Security of Industrial Enterprises - DTAI–2024, 2024. <https://dtai.tsue.uz/index.php/DTAI2024/article/view/rukhsora>
6. R Xolikova. Aspekti Otsenki Ekonomicheskoy Bezopasnosti Promyshlennykh Klasterov V Uzbekistane. Razvitiye I Analiz Uchrediteli: Shafi Science.2024. <https://e-itt.uz/index.php/eitt/article/view/1397>
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382195538_ASPEKTY_OCENKI_EKONOMICESKOJ_BEZOPASNOSTI_PROMYSLENNYH_KLASTEROV_V_UZBEKISTANE
7. US Department of State. <https://www.state.gov/artificial-intelligence/>
8. World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2024/01/chinas-data-and-ai-approach-is-changing-heres-what-that-means/>
9. Japan’s AI regulation for businesses. <https://law.asia/ai-regulation-businesses-japan/>